

A Study on the Traveling Salesman Problem by Using Brute Force and Nearest Neighbor Algorithms

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Abstract

There are several puzzles which can be analyzed by graph theoretic concepts. In this paper we select one of such puzzles, namely, Hamiltonian puzzle. Firstly, we discuss how the mathematicians' works upon Hamiltonian puzzle resulted in significant theoretical discoveries. Then we discuss how to solve the traveling salesman problem using brute force and nearest neighbor algorithms. Finally, the differences of these two algorithms are presented.

Keywords: puzzle, Hamiltonian circuit, Hamiltonian graph, traveling salesman problem, brute force algorithm, nearest neighbor algorithm.

Introduction

Graph theoretical ideas are highly utilized by real world applications. Especially the most important concept of paths, walks and circuits in graph theory are used in tremendous applications say traveling salesman problem. This leads to the development of new algorithms and new theorems that can be used in tremendous applications. This paper has been divided into three sections. First section gives the historical background of graph theory. Second section discuss Hamiltonian circuits and Hamiltonian graphs. Last section emphasizes how algorithms are utilized in the traveling salesman problem.

1. History of Graph Theory

The origin of graph theory started with the problem of Koinber Bridge, in 1735. This problem lead to the concept of Eulerian graph. Euler studied the problem of Koinberg bridge and constructed a structure to solve the problem called Eulerian graph. In 1840, A.F Mobius gave the idea of complete graph and bipartite graph and Kuratowski proved that they are planar by means of recreational problems. The concept of tree was implemented by Gustav Kirchhoff in 1845, and he employed graph theoretical ideas in the calculation of currents in electrical networks or circuits. In 1852, Thomas Guthrie found the famous four color problem. Then in 1856, Thomas. P. Kirkman and William R. Hamilton studied cycles on polyhydra and invented the concept called Hamiltonian graph by studying trips that visited certain sites exactly once. In 1913, H. Dudeney mentioned a puzzle problem. Eventhough the four color problem was invented it was solved only after a century by Kenneth Appel and Wolfgang Haken. This time is considered as the birth of graph theory.

1.1 Basic Definitions and Notations on Graphs

A **graph** $G = (V, E)$ consists of two sets: a finite set V of elements called **vertices** and a finite set E of elements called **edges**. Each edge is identified with a pair of vertices. We use the symbols v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots to represent the vertices and the symbols e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots to represent the edges of a graph. The vertices v_i and v_j associated with an edge e_i are called the **end vertices** of e_i .

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The edge e_l is then denoted as $e_l = v_i v_j$. All edges having the same pair of end vertices are called **parallel edges**. An edge is said to be **incident** on its end vertices. An edge incident on a single vertex is called a **loop**. A graph with neither loops nor parallel edges is called a **simple graph**. Two vertices are **adjacent** if they are the end vertices of some edge. If two edges have a common end vertex, then these edges are said to be **adjacent**. The number of edges incident on a vertex v_i is called the **degree of the vertex**, and is denoted by $d(v_i)$. A graph $G' = (V', E')$ is a **subgraph** of $G = (V, E)$ if $V' \subseteq V$ and $E' \subseteq E$. If G' is a subgraph of G , G is a **supergraph** of G' .

Let u and v be vertices of a graph G . A u - v **walk** W of G is a finite, alternating sequence

$$W : u = u_0 e_1 u_1 e_2 \dots u_{k-1} e_k u_k = v$$

of vertices and edges, beginning with vertex u and ending with vertex v , such that $e_i = u_{i-1} u_i$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. The number k (the number of occurrences of edges) is called the **length of W** . A u - v walk is closed or open depending on whether $u = v$ or $u \neq v$. A u - v **trail** is a u - v walk in which no edge is repeated, while a u - v **path** is a u - v walk in which no vertex is repeated. A nontrivial closed trail of a graph G is referred to as a **circuit** of G , and a circuit $v_1 v_2 \dots v_n v_1$ ($n \geq 3$) whose n vertices v_i are distinct is called a **cycle**.

A **complete graph** K_n is a graph with n vertices and an edge between every two vertices.

Figure 1. A complete graph K_5

A **weighted graph** is a graph in which each edge is assigned a weight (representing the time, distance, or cost of traversing that edge).

Figure 2. A weighted graph G

2. Hamiltonian Circuits and Hamiltonian Graphs

Hamiltonian graphs are named after Sir William Hamilton, an Irish Mathematician (1805-1865), who invented a puzzle, called Icosian game. The puzzle involved a dodecahedron (see Figure 3(a)) on which each of the 20 vertices was labelled by the name of some capital city in the world. The aim of the game was to construct, using the edges of the dodecahedron a closed trail of all the cities which traversed each city exactly once, beginning and ending at the same city.

The graph of the edges of the dodecahedron is given in Figure 3(b). We can solve Hamiltonian puzzle if we can find a circuit in the graph of Figure 3(b) that contains each vertex exactly once (except for the starting and ending vertex that appears twice).

Figure 3. Dodecahedron and its graph shown with the Hamiltonian circuit

2.1 Definitions

A **Hamiltonian circuit** is a circuit that contains each vertex of graph exactly once except for the first vertex, which is also the last.

A graph which possesses a Hamiltonian circuit is called a **Hamiltonian graph**.

Figure 4 has Hamiltonian circuit ABDCA as each vertex appears exactly once except A. So it is Hamiltonian graph.

Figure 4. A Hamiltonian graph G

2.2 Theorem

If G is a graph with n vertices, where $n \geq 3$ and $d(v) \geq \frac{n}{2}$, for every vertex v of G , then G is Hamiltonian.

Proof:

Assume that the result is not true. Then for some value $n \geq 3$, there is a non-

Hamiltonian graph H in which $d(v) \geq \frac{n}{2}$, for every vertex of H . In any spanning supergraph K of H , $d(v) \geq \frac{n}{2}$, for every vertex of K , since any proper supergraph of this form is obtained by adding more edges. Thus there is a maximal non-Hamiltonian graph G with n vertices and $d(v) \geq \frac{n}{2}$, for every v in G . Using this G , we obtain a contradiction.

Clearly, $G \neq K_n$, as K_n is Hamiltonian. Therefore there are non-adjacent vertices u and v in G . Let $G + uv$ be the supergraph of G by adding an edge between u and v . Since G is maximal non-Hamiltonian, $G + uv$ is Hamiltonian. Also, if C is a Hamiltonian circuit of $G + uv$, then C contains the edge uv , since otherwise C is a Hamiltonian circuit of G , which is not possible. Let this Hamiltonian circuit C be $u = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n = v, u$.

Now, let $S = \{v_i \in C : \text{there is an edge from } u \text{ to } v_{i+1} \text{ in } G\}$

and $T = \{v_j \in C : \text{there is an edge from } v \text{ to } v_j \text{ in } G\}$.

Then $v_n \notin T$, since otherwise there is an edge from v to $v_n = v$, that is a loop, which is impossible.

Also, $v_n \notin S$, since otherwise we again get a loop from u to $v_1 = u$. Therefore, $v_n \in S \cup T$ (Figure 5).

Let $|S|, |T|, |S \cup T|$ be the number of elements in S, T and $S \cup T$ respectively. So $|S \cup T| < n$. Also, for every edge incident with u , there corresponds one vertex v_i in S . Therefore, $|S| = d(u)$. Similarly, $|T| = d(v)$.

Now, if v_k is a vertex belonging to both S and T , there is an edge e joining u to v_{k+1} and an edge f joining v to v_k . This implies that $C' = v_1, v_{k+1}, v_{k+2}, \dots, v_n, v_k, v_{k-1}, \dots, v_2, v_1$ is a Hamiltonian circuit in G , which is a contradiction as G is non-Hamiltonian. This shows that there is no vertex v_k in $S \cap T$, so that $S \cap T = \emptyset$.

Thus $|S \cup T| = |S| + |T| - |S \cap T|$, gives $|S| + |T| = |S \cup T|$, so that

$d(u) + d(v) < n$. This is a contradiction, because $d(u) \geq \frac{n}{2}$, for all u in G , and so

$d(u) + d(v) \geq \frac{n}{2} + \frac{n}{2}$, giving $d(u) + d(v) \geq n$. Hence the theorem follows.

Figure 5.

2.3 Theorem

Let G be a graph with n vertices and let u and v be non-adjacent vertices in G such that $d(u)+d(v) \geq n$. Let $G+uv$ denote the supergraph of G obtained by joining u and v by an edge. Then G is Hamiltonian if and only if $G+uv$ is Hamiltonian.

Proof:

Let G be a graph with n vertices and suppose u and v are non-adjacent vertices in G such that $d(u)+d(v) \geq n$. Let $G+uv$ be the supergraph of G obtained by adding the edge uv . Let G be Hamiltonian. Then obviously $G+uv$ is Hamiltonian. Conversely, let $G+uv$ be Hamiltonian. We have to show that G is Hamiltonian. Then, as in Theorem 2.2, we get $d(u) + d(v) < n$, which contradicts the hypothesis that $d(u)+d(v) \geq n$. Hence G is Hamiltonian.

2.4 Definition

Let G be a graph with n vertices. If there are two non-adjacent vertices u_1 and v_1 in G such that $d(u_1)+d(v_1) \geq n$, join u_1 and v_1 by an edge to form the supergraph G_1 . Now, if there are two non-adjacent vertices u_2 and v_2 in G_1 such that $d(u_2)+d(v_2) \geq n$, join u_2 and v_2 by an edge to form supergraph G_2 . Continue in this way, recursively joining pairs of non-adjacent vertices whose degree sum is at least n until no such pair remains. The final supergraph thus obtained is called the **closure** of G and is denoted by $c(G)$. The example in Figure 6 illustrates the closure operation.

Figure 6.

2.5 Theorem

A graph G is Hamiltonian if and only if its closure $c(G)$ is Hamiltonian.

Proof:

Let $c(G)$ be the closure of the graph G . Since $c(G)$ is a supergraph of G , therefore, if G is Hamiltonian, then $c(G)$ is also Hamiltonian.

Conversely, let $c(G)$ be Hamiltonian. Let $G, G_1, G_2, \dots, G_{k-1}, G_k = c(G)$ be the sequence of graphs obtained by performing the closure procedure on G . Since $c(G) = G_k$ is obtained from G_{k-1} by setting $G_k = G_{k-1} + uv$, where u, v is a pair of non-adjacent vertices in G_{k-1} with $d(u)+d(v) \geq n$, therefore it follows that G_{k-1} is Hamiltonian. Similarly G_{k-2}, \dots, G_1 and thus G is Hamiltonian.

2.6 Theorem

In a complete graph with n vertices there are $(n-1)/2$ edge-disjoint Hamiltonian circuits, if n is an odd number, $n \geq 3$.

Proof:

A complete graph G of n vertices has $n(n-1)/2$ edges and Hamiltonian circuit in G contains n edges. Therefore the number of edge-disjoint Hamiltonian circuits in G cannot exceed $(n-1)/2$. When n is odd, we show there are $(n-1)/2$ edge-disjoint Hamiltonian circuits. The subgraph of a complete graph with n vertices shown in Figure 7 is a Hamiltonian circuit. Keeping the vertices fixed on a circle; rotate the polygonal pattern clockwise by $\frac{360}{n-1}, 2 \cdot \frac{360}{n-1}, \dots, \frac{n-3}{2} \cdot \frac{360}{n-1}$ degrees. We see that each rotation produces a Hamiltonian circuit that has no edge in common with any of the previous ones. Therefore, there are $(n-3)/2$ new Hamiltonian circuits., all disjoint from the one in Figure 7, and also edge-disjoint among themselves. Thus there are $(n-1)/2$ edge-disjoint Hamiltonian circuits.

Figure 7.

3. Traveling Salesman Problems and Real World Applications

One of the most famous applications of Hamiltonian graphs is the so-called traveling salesman problem.

A salesman is to make a tour of n cities, at the end of which he has to return to the head office from which he started. The salesman is not allowed to visit any intermediate city twice. The cost of the journey between any two cities is known. The problem asks for an efficient method for finding the least expensive tour. In principle, we can solve this problem by looking at all possible routes and choosing the one that involves the least cost or shortest time.

3.1 Nearest Neighbor Algorithm

- Step 1. Choose a starting point for the circuit. Call this vertex A.
- Step 2. Check all the edges joined to A, and choose one that has least weight. Proceed along this edge to the next vertex.
- Step 3. At each vertex you reach, check the edges from there to vertices not yet visited. Choose one with least weight. Proceed along this edge to the next vertex.
- Step 4. Repeat Step 3 until you have visited all the vertices.
- Step 5. Return to the starting vertex.

3.2 Example

A courier is based at the head office (A) and must deliver documents to four other offices (B,C,D, and E). The estimated time of travel (in minutes) between each of these offices is shown on the graph. The courier wants to visit the locations in an order that takes the least time. Use the nearest neighbor algorithm to find an approximate solution to this problem. Calculate the total time required to cover the chosen route.

Figure 8.

Now, we will find that the given problem has an approximate solution.

Choose a starting point. Let's start at A. Choose an edge with least weight joined to A. Both AB and AD have weight 9, which is less than the weights of the other two edges joined to A. We choose AD and keep a record of the circuit as we form it, AD.

To help ensure that we do not visit a vertex twice, we color the edges used.

Figure 9.

Now check edges joined to D, excluding DA (since we have already been to A). DC has weight 7, DB has weight 8, and DE has weight 5. DE has smallest weight, so proceed along DE to E. Our circuit begins this way, ADE.

Figure 10.

Now repeat the process at E. Check all edges from E that go to a vertex not yet visited. EC has weight 8 and EB has weight 3. Proceed along EB to B. Our circuit so far is as follows, ADEB.

Figure 11.

We have one vertex not yet visited. We go next to C and now have visited all the vertices. We return to our starting point A. Our Hamiltonian circuit is ADEBCA.

Its total weight is $9 + 5 + 3 + 10 + 13 = 40$.

Our advice to the courtier would thus be to visit the offices in the order shown in this circuit. This route will take about 40 minutes.

Figure 12.

We might think that we could get a quick route for the courier just by looking at the graph, rather than following the rules of the algorithm. We would be right. The Hamiltonian circuit ADEBCA, we found is not the minimum Hamiltonian circuit for the graph. However, the point of an approximate algorithm is that a computer can implement it without taking too much time, and most of the time it will give a reasonably good solution to the problem.

3.3 Brute Force Algorithm

Step 1. Make a list of all possible Hamiltonian circuits.

Step 2. Calculate the weight of each Hamilton circuit by adding up the weights of its edges.

Step 3. Choose the Hamiltonian circuit with the smallest total weight.

3.4 Example

A courier is based at the head office (A) and must deliver documents to four offices (B,C,D, and E). The estimated time of travel (in minutes) between each of these offices is shown on the graph. The courier wants to visit the locations in an order that takes the least time. Use the nearest neighbor algorithm to find an approximate solution to this problem. Calculate the total time required to cover the chosen route.

Now, we will find that the given problem has an approximate solution.

The number of vertices is $n = 5$.

So, the number of Hamiltonian circuits is $4! = 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 = 24$.

Possible Hamiltonian Circuits

	Hamiltonian Circuits	Total weight
1	ABCDEA	$9 + 10 + 7 + 5 + 20 = 51$
2	ABCEDA	$9 + 10 + 8 + 5 + 9 = 41$
3	ABDCEA	$9 + 8 + 7 + 8 + 20 = 52$
4	ABDECA	$9 + 8 + 5 + 8 + 13 = 43$
5	ABECDA	$9 + 3 + 8 + 7 + 9 = 36$
6	ABEDCA	$9 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 13 = 37$

	Hamiltonian Circuits	Total weight
7	ACBDEA	$13+10+8+5+20 = 56$
8	ACBEDA	$13+10+3+5+9 = 40$
9	ACDBEA	$13+7+8+3+20 = 51$
10	ACDEBA	$13+7+5+3+9 = 37$
11	ACEBDA	$13+8+3+8+9 = 41$
12	ACEDBA	$13+8+5+8+9 = 43$
13	ADBCEA	$9+8+10+8+20 = 55$
14	ADBECA	$9+8+3+8+13 = 41$
15	ADCBEA	$9+7+10+3+20 = 49$
16	ADCEBA	$9+7+8+3+9 = 36$
17	ADEBCA	$9+5+3+10+13 = 40$
18	ADECBA	$9+5+8+10+9 = 41$
19	AEBCDA	$20+3+10+7+9 = 49$
20	AEBDCA	$20+3+8+7+13 = 51$
21	AECBDA	$20+8+10+8+9 = 55$
22	AECDBA	$20+8+7+8+9 = 52$
23	AEDBCA	$20+5+8+10+13 = 56$
24	AEDCBA	$20+5+7+10+9 = 51$

This is still an approximate solution. If we check the total weights of all possible Hamiltonian circuits in the graph, we find the Hamiltonian circuits ABECDA and ADCEBA with total weights $9+3+8+7+9=36$ minutes and $9+7+8+3+9=36$ minutes. Thus the brute force algorithm will find the minimum Hamiltonian circuit of the graph.

Unfortunately, as soon as the number of cities increases beyond 10, we run into difficulties, since there is no known method that provides a simple and efficient solution for the problem, even if a computer is used.

If your computer can compute one million Hamiltonian circuits per second...

- $n = 6, 7, 8, 9$: instantaneous
- $n = 10$: about $\frac{1}{3}$ second
- $n = 11$: about 4 seconds
- $n = 12$: about 40 seconds
- $n = 13$: about 8 minutes
- $n = 14$: nearly 2 hours
- $n = 15$: a little over a day
- $n = 20$: over a million years.

3.5 Comparing Brute Force and Nearest Neighbor Algorithms

The brute force algorithm is optimal but inefficient. It is guaranteed to find a solution, but it may take an unreasonably long time to do so.

The nearest neighbor algorithm is efficient but nonoptimal. It is quick and easy, but does not always find the lowest weight Hamiltonian circuit.

Conclusion

We have now discussed the traveling salesman problem which follow from the study of the Hamiltonian circuits and Hamiltonian graphs. We have also described some of many theoretical and computational works which have been done on these problem. Although these theoretical and computational knowledge have not been used for real life problems of Myanmar, they have been successfully applied to transport management problems of cities and organizations of some other countries with remarkable outcomes of saving the required time, cost and energy, improving the efficiency of servicing processes and promoting the satisfaction of the customers. We hope that similar applications of mathematics that could help the social development of our people to some extent would appear soon.

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